

A STUDY OF SMALL SCALE INDUSTRIES IN JAMMU AND KASHMIR

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this paper is to study the small scale industries in Jammu and Kashmir. This paper is essentially in light of secondary source which is gathered from Journals, Magazines, News papers, Articles, Books and Academic sites and so on. The said consider that the small scale industries of Jammu and Kashmir gives an employment to a great number of people in rural and urban individuals of the state. The main reason of this study is to examine the growth execution and issues of small scale industries in Jammu and Kashmir.

KEYWORDS: *Small scale Industry, Employment, Growth performance, problems*

1. INTRODUCTION

Industrialisation is a key to financial improvement of a nation. The procedure of industrialisation helps in bridling and changing the crude assets into valuable purchaser items and viable means and devices of generation and in the improvement of framework. The industrial sector has a moderately high minimal inclination to spare and contributes altogether to the accomplishment of a self maintaining economy with proceeded with abnormal amounts of venture, increment in levels of wage and work. In a creating nation like India, where per capita wage is low and populace is high, with greater part living in towns, it is profoundly alluring to grow small scale industries which have limit of retaining increasingly jobless young people. In perspective of a few points of interest, for example, small incubation period, small venture, adjusted development and so on Small Scale Industries are not created completely in correlation of different industries. In Jammu and Kashmir, the extent of the Small Scale Industry is wide however the development of this industry is extremely thin. A few complexities are related with this industry and this is the reason as a result of which the advancement of SSI ends up noticeably basic. A few issues are discovered which ought to be fathomed for the proper development of the industry which contribute to Gross state Domestic product (GSDP). Presently, bank strategy and government approach give progression to SSI however issues are still there so these complexities ought to be settled. Jammu and Kashmir is isolated into urban region and country zone. For the most part, Small scale industries units are set up in country zone with bring down limit. So this is the most serious issue that Small scale industries can't get the advantage of urban culture.

2. OBJECTIVES

- ❖ To analyze the growth performance of small scale industries in Jammu and Kashmir.
- ❖ To explain the problems of small scale industries in Jammu and Kashmir.

3. DATA BASE AND METHODOLOGY

To fulfil the objectives of this paper, the secondary data were used and collected from Journals, Articles, Research papers and various government departments, different published sources (public and private) the more important among them were:

1. Digest of Statistics, Directorate of economics and statistics, Government of Jammu and Kashmir.
2. Jammu and Kashmir economic survey

4. GROWTH PERFORMANCE OF SMALL SCALE INDUSTRIES

The table shows the growth performance of small scale in Jammu and Kashmir from 2010-11 to 2015-16. The small scale industries sector assumes an urgent part in Jammu and Kashmir State. Other than giving employment opportunities to the jobless youth in the state.

Year	Units	Employment	Growth% Units	Growth% Employment
2010-11	53544	245774	-	-
2011-12	54714	251551	2.18	2.35
2012-13	55742	260393	1.87	3.51
2013-14	56660	267194	1.64	2.61
2014-15	57788	276680	1.99	3.55
2015-16	58596	283105	1.39	23.2

Source: Digest of Statistics Directorate of Economics and Statistics

Graph Shows Units and Employment of SSI in Jammu and Kashmir

The above table demonstrates that in 2010-11 the aggregate number of practical small scale industrial units in the Jammu and Kashmir state were 53544 creating occupation for 245774 people. Throughout the years the small scale sector has developed quickly in 2015-16. The quantity of units has expanded to 58596, giving work to 283105 people. The formal enrolment of units has enlisted 1.39% development amid the year 2015-16 as against 1.99% in relating year. Thus, employment likewise enlisted growth of 23.2% of every 2015-16 in contrast with 3.55% in relating year. Throughout the years the small scale sector has demonstrated a change by giving work to lakhs of peoples in the country. The quantity of small scale ventures has expanded from 53544 in the year 2010-11 to 58596 and during 2015-16 and the employment has expanded from 245774 in 2010-11 to 283105 during 2015-16. This demonstrates that there has a noteworthy increment in number of small scale units and furthermore in employment produced by them.

5. PROBLEMS OF SMALL SCALE INDUSTRIES

The major problems of small scale industries in Jammu and Kashmir which are briefly discussed as under.

(A). Lack of skilled labour

Ineffective human lively and unskilled labour make various issues for the survival of small enterprises. Non accessibility of adequate skilful labour in the country part makes issue to small scale sectors of Jammu and Kashmir.

(B). Non Availability of credit assistance:

The deficiency of capital and lack of accessibility of credit assistance is the primary driver of this issue. After nationalization, banks have begun financing this segment. These endeavours are still under strain with the issue of insufficient accessibility of funds.

(C). Low Availability of Raw materials:

The issues happen because of damaged availability of raw materials. Non-accessibility of sufficient amount of crude materials, lessened nature of crude materials, high cost of crude materials, and absence of information of entrepreneur's people regarding the matter of government policy and programmes are different issues for small scale industries of the state.

(D). Absence of proper marketing

Another critical issue facing by small scale units is the absence of proper marketing. In the absence of proper marketing, their items assess fundamentally with the nature of the result of large- scale units. They are not in a position to get essential data about the market i.e. about the opposition, taste, enjoying, detesting of the purchasers and winning style.

(E). Lack of infrastructural facilities

Small scale industries are in inflexible position to use current apparatuses and gear in their system of generation keeping in mind the end goal to battle with large scale industries. A large portion of the small units use preservationist and conventional innovation and gear. Absence of suitable innovation and equipment make a principle unverifiable impede for the extension of small scale sectors. Insufficient and improper transportation and correspondence framework will make the working of various units more complex.

(F). Other problems

Other than the above issues, small-scale units have been of obliged by various different issues too. They incorporate poor venture arranging, administrative insufficiencies, old and universal outlines, power cuts, Low availability of wage rate, and absence of sufficient incentives, Because of every one of these issues the development of small-scale industries couldn't achieve a regarded stage.

6. CONCLUSION

The present study we can conclude that the Small scale industries of Jammu and Kashmir have seen some checked development, however not agreeable. The commitment of small scale industries in utilized age by and by strengthens the significance of this part to solve the different issues with which the state economy is gone up against with. The small scale industries however imperative because of many reasons yet, can't take care of the issue of large-scale joblessness especially among the informed youth. The future any expectation of the state with respect to the age of significant employment avenues for the informed youth lies in the advancement of present day small scale ventures .Although small scale enterprises if grew legitimately can possibly produce work yet, alone it can't free the state from the grasp of backwardness and neediness.

REFERENCES

- [1] Sharma, J. b. (1990). Small scale industries, problems and prospects. Anmol publication. New Delhi.
- [2] Butt, A.K. (2005). Strategising industrial development in Jammu and Kashmir. New century publications, New Delhi.
- [3] Ahmad, B.F. and Dar, B.A. (2013). Small scale industries in Jammu and Kashmir (J&k): Growth performance and challenges. *International NGO Journal*. Vol-8 No-2 pp: 38-43
- [4] Ziniya, N.S. (2014). Complexity of small scale industry in India. *International multidisciplinary research Journal*, Vol- 1 No-1 pp- 1-5
- [5] Chaudhari, T.P. and patil, G.S.(2014). Problems of small scale Industries in India. *International Journal of Engineering and management research*. Vol- 4, No- 2 pp- 19-21
- [6] Economic survey (2015-16). Directorate of Economics and Statistics, planning and development Department, Jammu and Kashmir.
- [7] Digest of Statistics (2015-16). Directorate of Economics and Statistics, Jammu and Kashmir.